

TEACHING ENGLISH IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Mavlonova Shahzoda Turg'unovna

Senior Lecturer,

Department of Foreign Languages, Fergana State University

Email: mavlonovashahzoda1975@gmail.com

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Abstract. *The educational goal, as a socio-pedagogical and linguodidactic concept, can be defined as follows in application to teaching English: it is a means of determining the content of education in the form of a social order from society and the state for learning English as one of the subjects in special schools, organizing the teaching process, and predetermining the achievement of certain results.*

Key words: *authentic material, discourse, communicative competence, linguistic competence, sociolinguistic competence, pragmatic competence, types of speech activity, practical goal, educational goal, developmental goal.*

INTRODUCTION

On December 10, 2012, the Decree PQ-1875 "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Learning Foreign Languages" set the main goal of improving the system of teaching foreign languages to the young generation, preparing specialists who can speak these languages fluently, creating opportunities for them to widely use the achievements of world civilization and information resources, and to develop international cooperation and communication.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities," adopted on June 15, 2021, and effective from January 1, 2022, became the legal basis for fundamental reforms in the field. This law guarantees the rights of children with disabilities to education, participation in social life, and equal access to information, accelerating the process of integrating inclusive education into the national education system.

Every state, every nation is strong not only with its underground and surface natural resources, military power, and production capacity, but first and foremost with its high culture and spirituality. Therefore, large-scale works are being carried out in our republic to fundamentally renew and reform the education system in order to raise a healthy and well-rounded generation.

Uzbekistan's multicultural and multilingual "landscape" serves as an effective basis for developing a person's language competence. English language education, or as N. Galskova puts it, "Linguocultural education," further expands the opportunities and boundaries for the young generation to obtain, transmit, and interact with new and useful information (information).

The educational goal, as a socio-pedagogical and linguodidactic concept, can be defined as follows in application to teaching English: it is a means of determining the content of education in the form of a social order from society and the state for learning English as one of the subjects in general education, organizing the teaching process, and predetermining the achievement of certain results. What is English taught for in school? It is a term-concept used as an answer to this question. In specialized schools, English is taught to students with (1) practical goal, (2) general educational goal, (3) upbringing goal, and (4) developmental goal. In achieving the practical goal of teaching English, the final practical goal of teaching English in the general education school course is listening comprehension and reading, i.e., obtaining information in a foreign language by listening and reading. Intermediate practical goals are interpreted differently: in grade I, listening comprehension and speaking are considered practical goals; in grades II-IV, listening comprehension and speaking are also practical goals, while reading and writing serve as means to repeat and consolidate the language material learned orally; in grades V-VI, from the types of speech activity, listening comprehension, speaking, and reading are intermediate practical goals, writing is a practical means; in grades VII-IX, listening comprehension and reading are practical goals, speaking and writing are means.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

It is known that any goal arises due to a need. In methodological literature, when analyzing needs, objective and subjective needs are distinguished based on educational conditions. Objective need: a) psychological characteristics of English learners according to age, native language, interests, aptitude for learning English; b) levels of knowledge, skills, and abilities to be mastered in types of speech activity in English; c) information on program requirements for students' knowledge, skills, and abilities in English, based on state and society demands, i.e., from the social order.

The goals of teaching English are determined based on the conditions of inclusive education and the demands of society and the individual as a key component of this system. The goal, in turn, determines the content, principles of teaching English, as well as methods and technologies arising from the characteristics of the teacher and students' activities.

In achieving the practical goal of teaching English, special topics and language material are selected for the types of speech activity, most of the study time is devoted to learning them, i.e., most exercises are performed in that type(s) of speech activity. The practical goal is achieved through mastering linguistic, sociolinguistic, and pragmatic competences. Competence (ability, virtue), as known, consists of a set

of knowledge, skills, abilities, and personal characteristics. Competence includes smaller concepts.

In inclusive education conditions in primary grades, teaching English is a collaborative activity of the teacher and student aimed from goal to result. In primary education, to achieve from goal to result, the following tasks are performed: – providing the student with two types of knowledge, namely, algorithmic rules regarding language (phonetics, graphics and orthography, lexicon, grammar) necessary for participating in the speech process, and information that acquires social importance and will be useful throughout the student's life; the student is taught to view the world picture with a new perspective through the eyes of an English speaker and consequently to harmoniously feel universal and national values; – through exercises such as reading and writing, reading and listening, reading and speaking, listening and reading, listening and writing, listening and speaking, the four types of speech activity: listening comprehension, speaking, reading, and writing skills are developed in interconnection.

CONCLUSION

Uzbekistan's multicultural and multilingual "landscape" serves as an effective basis for developing a person's language competence. English language education, or as N. Galskova puts it, "Linguocultural education," further expands the opportunities and boundaries for the young generation to obtain, transmit, and interact with new and useful information.

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